

A Selective Spectrophotometric Determination of Molybdenum(V) as its 3-Hydroxyflavone Complex[#]

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3-Hydroxyflavone (HL) has been reported¹ as a spectrophotometric reagent for the determination of molybdenum(VI) at pH 1.5. However, as the reagent forms coloured complexes with many metal ions, the above procedure is less selective and finds little application in the analysis of complex samples containing varied compositions. In our investigations, we have observed that molybdenum(V) obtained by ascorbic acid reduction of molybdenum(VI), forms a similar coloured complex with HL as that formed by molybdenum(VI), which upon extraction with chloroform from sulphuric acid media, not only improves the stability, scope of applicability and Beer's law range to a much wider limit but also suppresses the interferences of many metal ions effectively without causing any change in the sensitivity of the coloured reaction. Accordingly, the extractive behaviour of Mo^V-HL complex has been studied with a view to its application to molybdenum determination in technical and synthetic samples of diversified matrix.

Results and Discussion

Molybdenum(VI) is reduced to pentavalent state by ascorbic acid in 1 M sulphuric acid medium², in cold, which forms a yellow coloured complex with 3-hydroxyflavone, extractable into chloroform. The ions Se^{IV}, V^V, Fe^{III} and Cr^{VI} are also reduced to their lower valent states under the conditions of the method which either do not form coloured complexes with the reagent, or if coloured, are not extracted at all and hence are non-interfering. It has been found that 10–40 mg ml⁻¹ ascorbic

acid gives a constant absorbance of Mo–HL complex and hence 20 mg ml⁻¹ amount is used in the method. The complex shows an absorption maximum at 405 nm, whereas the absorption of reagent being negligible at this wavelength. Of the various solvents tried for the extraction of the complex, maximum absorbance is observed in benzene and chloroform. The colour in benzene is stable only for 30 min, whereas it remains unchanged in chloroform even after two days and hence the latter is preferred for further investigations. Single extraction with 10 ml of chloroform is sufficient for quantitative transfer (100%) of molybdenum complex into the solvent phase. After the addition of HL, the extraction of Mo complex into chloroform is very fast and no change is observed in the absorbance when the shaking time is varied from 30 s to 1.5 min; 30 s of shaking is enough for the quantitative extraction of the complex into chloroform.

The formation and absorbance of the complex is greatly influenced by the acidity of extraction, keeping the acidity of reduction constant at 1 M H₂SO₄. The absorbance increases considerably with the acid concentration, reaching maximum when extracted at 0.1–0.18 M H₂SO₄. Further addition of the acid decreases the absorbance slightly. Hence, extraction at 0.15 M H₂SO₄ is recommended in the procedure. For 0.4–0.6 ml of 4.2 × 10⁻³ M HL in acetone, the absorbance has been found to be maximum which decreases considerably with further increase in reagent concentration. So 0.5 ml HL is used in this method. Formation of complex is not complete when HL is taken directly

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in chloroform itself and shaken even for 20 min. The complex is stable for more than 2 days in chloroform extract. Beer's law is obeyed in the concentration range 0–3.2 $\mu\text{g Mo ml}^{-1}$. The molar absorptivity and Sandell's sensitivity are $3.65 \times 10^4 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $0.0026 \mu\text{g Mo cm}^{-2}$ respectively at 405 nm. The mean absorbance, standard deviation and relative mean error for five replicate determinations of $2.0 \mu\text{g Mo ml}^{-1}$ are found to be $0.760, \pm 0.0015$ and 0.268% respectively. In the extracted species, the ratio of Mo–HL is found to be 1 : 2 as determined by Job's method of continuous variations and mole-ratio method.

Effect of diverse ions : To test the tolerance limits under optimum conditions, 30 μg molybdenum is determined in presence of the respective foreign ions. 0.1 g of Na_2 EDTA is also added prior to the extraction of Mo for masking V^{V} and Sn^{II} . The amounts of the ions (mg ml^{-1} in parenthesis) causing $< 1\%$ error are : $\text{Fe}^{\text{II,III}}$, Cu^{II} , Ni^{II} , Co^{II} , $\text{Cr}^{\text{III,IV}}$, Mn^{II} , Ti^{IV} , U^{VI} , Ce^{IV} , Al^{III} , Zn^{II} , Ag^{I} , Cd^{II} , Sb^{V} , Hg^{II} , Pb^{II} , Bi^{III} , Zr^{IV} , V^{V} (1.0); Se^{IV} (0.5); Sn^{II} (0.2); Os^{VIII} , Rh^{III} , Ru^{III} , Re^{VII} (0.05); sulphate, acetate, nitrate, EDTA, chloride, phosphate, thiourea (10.0); thiocyanate (3.0); tartrate (2.5); citrate (0.6) and glycerol (0.1 ml).

Applications : The method has been successfully applied to the analysis of flue dust, steels and several synthetic samples containing many analytically important elements in concentrations higher than normally met with. The results are found in good agreement with the amount of Mo added/certified value (Table 1). The proposed method is simple, rapid, accurate and is found to be superior to many existing ones in respect of selectivity^{1,3} and sensitivity⁴.

TABLE 1—ANALYSIS OF MOLYBDENUM IN DIFFERENT SAMPLES

Sl. no.	Sample composition Matrix (mg)	Mo added μg	Mo found* μg
1.	Bi(1), Os(0.1), Hg(2)	25	25.2
2.	Fe(0.1), V(1), Cu(3)	20	20.2
3.	Co(1), Ni(2), Cr(2), Fe(2)	30	29.9
4.	U(1), Bi(2), Zn(3), Ce(1)	10	10.2
5.	Flue dust (Copper Corporation of India)	10	9.87
6.	British Chemical Standards (BCS) No 406/1	1% ^a	0.97%

*Average of duplicate analyses. ^aCertified value.

Experimental

Spectral curves and routine analytical measurements were made with a Hitachi U-2000 spectrophotometer fitted with quartz cells of 10 mm optical path-length.

Stock solution of molybdenum(vi) 10 mg ml^{-1} was prepared from $\text{Na}_2\text{MoO}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (E. Merck) and standardised by oxine⁵ method. Two working solutions (10 and $100 \mu\text{g Mo ml}^{-1}$) were prepared by appropriate dilution of the standard solution. All other reagents used were of analytical grade. Stock solutions of diverse ions were prepared from their corresponding salts. 3-Hydroxyflavone (HL) was prepared by the reported method⁶ and it was dissolved in acetone to give $4.2 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$ solution. Chloroform (Qualigens SQ) was distilled and the fraction distilling at $60\text{--}61^\circ$ was collected for use. Ascorbic acid (G.R., S. M. Chemicals) and $2.5 \text{ M H}_2\text{SO}_4$ were used.

Synthetic samples were prepared by mixing molybdate and other metal ion solutions to get the desired composition. Reverberatory flue dust sample (0.1 g) was dissolved as described earlier⁷ and aliquots (1 ml) were used for analysis. Steel sample (0.1 g) was dissolved in minimum volume (5 ml) of aqua regia by heating slowly on a sand-bath. The solution was evaporated to dryness and the residue treated with water (10 ml) and $2.5 \text{ M H}_2\text{SO}_4$ (5 ml). The resulting solution was filtered and the volume was made up to 100 ml.

Procedure : To a known volume (1 ml) of the sample solution containing upto $32 \mu\text{g}$ of molybdenum(vi), were added $2.5 \text{ M H}_2\text{SO}_4$ (0.6 ml) and solid ascorbic acid (200 mg). The solution was warmed to dissolve ascorbic acid followed by addition of distilled water (7.6 ml) and $4.2 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$ solution of 3-hydroxyflavone (0.5 ml). The contents were well mixed and then equilibrated with chloroform (10 ml) for 30 s. After phase separation, the organic extract was passed through Whatman No. 41 filter paper and absorbance of the yellow complex was measured at 405 nm against a reagent blank. The amount of molybdenum was deduced from a calibration curve prepared under identical conditions of the method.

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